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Title: High temporal resolution of airborne Ambrosia pollen measurements above the source reveals emission characteristics

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Abstract: The aim of this study was to setup a field experiment that will collect suitable data for parameterizing the release of Ambrosia pollen. The study took place on the Pannonian plain during three flowering seasons: 2014, 2015 and 2016. The sampling of airborne pollen was performed using volumetric spore traps at 0.5 m and 5 m above the canopy level of a strong homogenous Ambrosia artemisiifolia L. field (10 m × 10 m) in three temporal resolutions: 1 h, 7.5 minutes and 1.07 minutes. This high temporal resolution revealed characteristics that were hitherto unknown. Pollen production per day was estimated to range from 6.38 billion to 770 billion pollen grains for the whole experimental field. Measurements of meteorological parameters included: temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, precipitation, wind speed and wind direction. Weak correlations between pollen concentration and meteorological parameters were obtained, indicating nonlinear relationships among them. The distribution of pollen concentration with respect to meteorological parameters showed that high pollen concentrations coincide with temperature in the interval 20-24°C, and that relative humidity of around 95% can delay or even switch off the emission, while the turbulent kinetic energy of a wind less than 0.1 m² s⁻² is sufficient for lifting the pollen into the air. The test of the new model for Ambrosia pollen emission processes showed a strong correlation between measured and modeled data when the estimated emission capacity for the field was in the range of 45-75 billion pollen grains per day.

ATMENV-D-18-00419R1 High temporal resolution of airborne *Ambrosia* pollen measurements above the source reveals emission characteristics

Reviewer #1: I appreciate the work of the authors to elaborate this new version, which I find much improved and highly interesting. I have very few comments now that I summarize here:

Reply: The authors thank to the reviewer for helping us to improve the quality of the paper.

Reviewer #1: l. 49-50, I do not know the policy of Atmospheric environment with regard to Keywords but I would suggest not use in them words already appearing in the title. So, I propose to consider as Keyword Ragweed (instead of Ambrosia) and pollen production (added or instead pollen emission).

Reply: There is no strict rule regarding the words used in the title and as Keywords in Atmospheric Environment. In the new version we have added “ragweed” instead of Ambrosia, however we kept “pollen emission” since the emission process is in the focus of the paper.

Reviewer #1: l. 163, consider to add "of" between "in the source area and" and "daily rate"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 188, consider to add "the" between "During" and "entire"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 188, consider to add "," after "period"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 203, consider to add "," after "A. artemisiifolia plants"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 208, consider to move "(" from before "in case" to before "i.e. turbulence"

Reply: It is moved in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 209, consider to add "," between "while" and "in case" and again "," after "velocities"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 209-210, change from "together with Lanzoni traps is expected to give information on background levels of A. artemisiifolia airborne pollen concentrations." To "it is expected to give information on background levels of A. artemisiifolia airborne pollen concentrations together with Lanzoni traps."

Reply: It is changed in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 212, consider to add "," after "3 h"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 235, consider to add "," between "concentrations" and "a meteorological"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 548, consider to add "Ambrosia" in the title

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 564, add "I" at the end of "Rantio-Lehtimäk"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 662, consider to add "of 10x10 m² surface" after "A. artemissiifolia"

Reply: It is added in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 664, Is it correct or precise enough to talk about "sampling frequency"? What about using "resolution" instead of "frequency"?

Reply: It is corrected to “resolution” in the new version.

Reviewer #1: l. 679, I think that "and" between "parameter" and "in the future" is not needed. I propose to eliminate it.

Reply: It is eliminated in the new version.

1 **High temporal resolution of airborne *Ambrosia* pollen measurements above the source reveals**
2 **emission characteristics**

3
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26 **Abstract**

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28 The aim of this study was to setup a field experiment that will collect suitable data for
29 parameterizing the release of *Ambrosia* pollen. The study took place on the Pannonian plain
30 during three flowering seasons: 2014, 2015 and 2016. The sampling of airborne pollen was
31 performed using volumetric spore traps at 0.5 m and 5 m above the canopy level of a strong
32 homogenous *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L. field (10 m × 10 m) in three temporal resolutions: 1 h,
33 7.5 minutes and 1.07 minutes. This high temporal resolution revealed characteristics that were
34 hitherto unknown. Pollen production per day was estimated to range from 6.38 billion to 770
35 billion pollen grains for the whole experimental field. Measurements of meteorological
36 parameters included: temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, precipitation, wind speed
37 and wind direction. Weak correlations between pollen concentration and meteorological
38 parameters were obtained, indicating nonlinear relationships among them. The distribution of
39 pollen concentration with respect to meteorological parameters showed that high pollen
40 concentrations coincide with temperature in the interval 20-24°C, and that relative humidity of
41 around 95% can delay or even switch off the emission, while the turbulent kinetic energy of a
42 wind less than $0.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ is sufficient for lifting the pollen into the air. The test of the new model
43 for *Ambrosia* pollen emission processes showed a strong correlation between measured and
44 modeled data when the estimated emission capacity for the field was in the range of 45-75
45 billion pollen grains per day.

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49 *Keywords:* aerobiology; ragweed; measurements; pollen emission; meteorological conditions;
50 turbulent kinetic energy

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60 **1. Introduction**

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62 Airborne pollen is considered as the main trigger of allergic diseases that affects as many as 15
63 million people in Europe (Bousquet, 2013). Avoidance of the exposure to airborne pollen is an
64 important part of managing allergic symptoms (Peden and Reed, 2010). Effective allergy
65 management requires the support of measurements and models that can provide patients and
66 medical doctors with temporally resolved information on the quantity of allergenic pollen
67 suspended in the atmosphere. This quantity is known to vary with climate, meteorological
68 conditions, geography and vegetation (Scheifinger et al., 2013) but also with the location of the
69 measurement system with respect to the distance from the emission source (Raynor et al., 1968).

70 Forecasting airborne pollen concentrations relies on the analysis of relationships between
71 airborne pollen concentrations and various environmental variables (Scheifinger et al., 2013).
72 Whatever method is used to explore relationships (e.g. regression analysis or more elaborate
73 machine learning techniques) the analysis should be performed on datasets able to describe the full
74 variability of the analysed phenomena. Sofiev et al. (2006) theoretically argued that if proper
75 emission fluxes could be developed, the atmospheric models could provide reliable estimates of the
76 atmospheric transport of pollen. To achieve this goal, detailed measurements of the exact emission
77 from the plants are required.

78 The Hirst-type volumetric method (Hirst, 1952) is commonly used for measuring
79 atmospheric concentrations of allergenic pollen. The standardized methodology suggests that the
80 sampling should be performed at the roof level to avoid the influence of local sources (Galán et al.,
81 2014). Many studies have shown that roof-level measurements underestimate concentrations near
82 the source and this is particularly pronounced for airborne pollen coming from herbaceous plants
83 (Alcázar and Comtois, 2000; Rantio-Lehtimäki et al., 1991; Raynor et al., 1973; Spieksma et al.,
84 2000). The further pollen is transported from the source, mixing within the lower atmospheric
85 boundary layer is more efficient. This leads to dilution of emitted concentrations (Chamecki and
86 Meneveau, 2011; Sofiev, 2017).

87 Devices used for sampling in operational aerobiological networks (e.g. Lanzoni VPPS,
88 Burkard Spore Trap, Burkard Scientific SporeWatch Sampler) are constructed to continuously
89 sample a known volume of air through an orifice and deposit the suspended particles on a sticky
90 surface. The speed at which the sampling surface moves behind the orifice determines the temporal
91 resolution of the collected dataset. To enable continuous work for several days, the speed of rotation
92 of the sampling surface is usually set to 2 mm h^{-1} which, with the standard sampling orifice 14 mm
93 $\times 2 \text{ mm}$, limits the finest temporal resolution to 1 h (BAF, 1995).

94 Such a coarse temporal resolution is sufficient to describe seasonal patterns, while
95 monitoring at roof-level reflects the regional variability that includes both the emission and the
96 atmospheric transport. However, for detailed insights into emission processes, higher temporal
97 resolution is required for the detection of variability in the immediate vicinity of the source.

98 Common ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.) is a noxious invasive species introduced to
99 Europe from North America. One of the main centres of its European distribution is the Pannonian
100 Plain which is proved to be an important source of aeroallergens throughout Europe (Smith et al.,
101 2013). Common ragweed is often found in farmlands. It is a source of highly allergenic pollen,
102 which is reported to induce asthma more often than other pollen types (Dahl et al., 1999). *A.*
103 *artemisiifolia* L. shows clear diurnal periodicity with respect to the opening of male flowers and the
104 release of pollen that corresponds to the increase of temperature and the decrease of relative
105 humidity (Bianchi et al., 1959). However, threshold values for flowering were observed in the
106 laboratory conditions and real-life tests in the open field are required to confirm their suitability for
107 mechanistic parameterization of the emission process. Two major field experiments were conducted
108 in the USA to provide data needed for exploring the dispersion and deposition of ragweed pollen
109 grains (Martin et al., 2009; Raynor et al., 1970). These setups successfully described the temporal
110 distribution of concentration peaks recorded above the source (Ogden et al., 1969), as well as the
111 biological aspect of pollen maturation, presentation and release (Martin et al., 2009; 2010). All
112 these mentioned studies showed that pollen emission processes are complicated and require
113 measurements in high temporal resolution to capture the variability and the conditions in the field.
114 In addition, none of these studies sampled pollen at the sufficient temporal resolution to enable
115 more precise assessment of emission patterns and flux, which is needed for parameterization in
116 dispersion models (Prank et al., 2013). Finally, all previous studies of ragweed pollen emission
117 have been conducted in North America which is the native range of *A. artemisiifolia* L. distribution
118 and the obtained relationships need to be confirmed with measurements in its invasive range as
119 suggested by Ogden et al. (1969), who assumed that the location with different meteorological
120 conditions could lead to shifts in the emission.

121 The first aim of this study was to setup a field experiment to collect suitable data for the
122 characterization of *A. artemisiifolia* airborne pollen release from the source and the influence of
123 meteorological conditions. Secondly, the collected samples are expected to show if a more
124 temporally detailed analysis brings additional information about the emission processes.

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128 2. Materials and methods

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130 2.1. Location of the study area and *Ambrosia* pollen source characteristics

131

132 The study was conducted in Backi Maglic (45°21'46.3" N, 19°31'55.9" E), situated in the Pannonian
133 part of Serbia (Fig. 1A) which is known as being heavily invaded by *Ambrosia* plants (Skjøth et al.,
134 2010). The local source of *Ambrosia* airborne pollen was created by covering a 10 m × 10 m patch
135 with soil from a heavily infested agriculture area. This introduced a notable seed pool and resulted
136 in growth of numerous ragweed plants. After the plants emerged, the source area was modified to
137 contain 500 equally distributed *Ambrosia* plants, which allowed for full development of the plant
138 habitus and thus lead to full pollen emission potential. An additional effort was made to keep the
139 homogenous *Ambrosia* population free from other weeds. This procedure has been repeated in
140 2014, 2015 and 2016.

141 Heavily infested backyards in populated areas show similar environments and thus the
142 source area prepared represents the real exposure risk of inhabitants to airborne ragweed pollen. In
143 order to ensure that the created local source area dominates in airborne pollen samples, all ragweed
144 plants were removed within the range of at least 500 m around the source. The given buffer is
145 considered sufficient for sensors measuring at 0.5 m and 5.5 m above the canopy (Burba and
146 Anderson, 2005) and also is in line with findings that only 5% of ragweed pollen is transferred
147 further then 100m from the source area (Raynor et al., 1970).

148 The number and percentage of plants that release pollen were recorded on the experimental
149 field daily, to determine the time of the full pollen release. In all three seasons all plants started to
150 release pollen by 15th August. Each day starting from this date, between one and three male flowers
151 per inflorescence matured and released pollen.

152 In order to determine the strength of our pollen source we estimated pollen production per
153 plant following the methodology described in Fumanal et al. (2007). Five fully developed plants
154 from different locations of the source were chosen. For each plant we counted the number of:
155 racemes (nR), male heads in five representative racemes (nMH) and male flowers in five
156 representative male heads (nMF). Finally, total of 15 closed male flowers were extracted (five from
157 each chosen plant) and macerated separately in 100 microliters of distilled H₂O. Complete
158 suspension of pollen from each flower is transferred to a microscopic slide. The complete surface of
159 the slide was analysed using light microscope (×200 magnification) and all pollen grains were
160 counted to get the number of pollen grains per flower (nPG). The total pollen production per plant
161 was computed from the measured parameters ($P = nR \times nMH \times nMF \times nPG$) and we presented both

162 the average so as the maximum and minimum value. Apart from total pollen production per plant,
163 knowing the number of plants in the source area and of daily rate male flowers are opened (1-3 per
164 male head) we were able to estimate range of daily pollen production of the pollen source area
165 which is required input for the emission model. The lower limit is obtained by multiplying number
166 of plants in source area with average pollen production per plant assuming only one male flower is
167 opened per male head and the upper limit is obtained by multiplying number of plants in source
168 area with average pollen production per plant assuming three male flowers are opened per male
169 head.

170 On 2nd September 2015 (18:00-20:00) the source was removed to confirm that the majority
171 of pollen recorded above the source was coming from the plants beneath. Also, on 1st September
172 2016 (9:00-10:00), half of the source was removed (central square 7 m × 7 m) to explore the effect
173 of the source size on pollen records (Supplementary material Fig. S1). The management of the
174 source shook plants and resulted in a notable artificial pollen release. Although these periods give
175 estimates of the potential exposure for workers that eradicate ragweed during flowering, we
176 removed these data when analysing normal emission patterns and relationships with meteorological
177 data.

178

Fig. 1. (A) Location of the regional Hirst-type pollen samplers in relation to study area and (B) Digital Surface Model depicting the height of objects surrounding the artificial *Ambrosia* pollen source in Backi Maglic and location of meteorological station and Burkard Scientific SporeWatch samplers in the center (asterisk) so as Lanzoni VPPS2010 samplers (filled triangle, filled circle and filled square) installed at 1.5 m above the ground in close vicinity of the pollen source.

179 2.2. Airborne pollen data

180

181 Simultaneous sampling of airborne pollen and meteorological parameters was performed in the
182 centre of the artificially created *Ambrosia* pollen source during three flowering seasons: 21th August
183 – 12th September 2014, 16th July – 5th September 2015 and 29th July – 8th September 2016. In
184 addition to measurements in the centre of the source, to serve as control for background levels,
185 pollen concentrations were recorded at 1.5 m above ground level in close vicinity of the source
186 towards dominant wind directions (20 m towards North-West in 2015, 15 m towards East in 2015
187 and 60 m towards East in 2015 and 2016). During the entire study period, airborne *Ambrosia* pollen
188 was recorded also at regional aerobiological stations situated on the roof-level in Sombor, Vrbas
189 and Novi Sad (Fig. 1A).

190 The sampling of airborne pollen was performed using volumetric spore traps of the Hirst
191 design (Hirst, 1952). Air is sucked into the trap at a rate of 10 l min⁻¹ through a 2 mm × 14 mm
192 orifice. Behind the orifice the air flows over a slowly rotating drum that moves past the inlet and is
193 covered with an adhesive coated, transparent plastic tape. Particles in the air land on the tape to give
194 a time-related sample (Emberlin, 2000), while the relationship between the rotation speed and the
195 width of the orifice determines the maximal temporal resolution. In addition to 6 standard 7-day
196 Lanzoni traps (three regional VPPS2000 aerobiological stations and three VPPS2010 traps in the
197 close vicinity of local source), which had drums rotating at 2 mm h⁻¹, allowing for maximal 1 h
198 temporal resolution, we decided to collect pollen above the source using Burkard Scientific
199 SporeWatch samplers that allowed adjusting the full rotation of the rotating drum to 21 h resulting
200 in maximal 7.5-minute temporal resolution of the samples. Two SporeWatch samplers were
201 installed in the centre of the *A. artemisiifolia* pollen source area. One was set to sample air at 1.5 m
202 above ground level, which is 0.5 m above the canopy of *A. artemisiifolia* plants, and the other was
203 set to sample air at 6 m above ground level. Since the footprint area increases with the height of the
204 sensor and the contribution of the area under the sensor decreases (Burba and Anderson, 2005), the
205 lower SporeWatch sampler was expected to collect pollen from the experimental pollen source area.
206 The SporeWatch sampler installed at 6m above the ground was expected to provide data for
207 exploring the concentration profile in case of notable vertical wind velocities (i.e. turbulence),
208 while, in case of notable horizontal wind velocities, it is expected to give information on
209 background levels of *A. artemisiifolia* airborne pollen concentrations together with Lanzoni traps. In
210 2015, on 1st September and 2nd September, the full rotation of the rotating drum in SporeWatch
211 traps in the middle of the experimental field (both at 1.5 m and 6 m above ground level) was set to 3
212 h, resulting in maximal 1.07-minute temporal resolution of the samples. This allowed us to get

213 additional insight in the variability of airborne pollen concentrations during the period of high
214 emission (6:00-12:00).

215 Collected samples from both types of samplers (Burkard and Lanzoni) were prepared and
216 analysed to retrieve average pollen concentrations per unit of time following the European
217 Aerobiology Society's minimum recommendations (Galán et al., 2014) and expressed as pollen
218 grains per cubic metre of air (pollen grains m^{-3}) (Galán et al., 2017). After the removal from the
219 trap, the tape was divided into 48 mm segments. This corresponded to 24-h periods (full rotation of
220 the drum every 168 h, i.e. 7 days), 3-h periods (full rotation of the drum every 21 h) and 25.71-
221 minute periods (full rotation of the drum every 3 h). Each segment was mounted between a glass
222 slide and a cover slip using glycerine-gelatine stained with basic fuchsin. The slides were
223 examined using light microscopy ($\times 200$ magnification) by counting all pollen grains of *A.*
224 *artemisiifolia* as the slide is scanned along three longitudinal transects ($\approx 20\%$ of the total area). The
225 counts were annotated for every 2 mm segment to allow calculation 1-h, 7.5-minute and 1.07-
226 minute concentration, as determined by the rotation speed of the drum and width of the sampling
227 orifice.

228 Due to technical issues with the pollen and spore traps (i.e. stop of rotation of the drum)
229 some data are missing from the analysis.

230

231 2.3. Meteorological data

232

233 With the aim of exploring the relationships between environmental conditions and recorded
234 airborne pollen concentrations, a meteorological station with temperature (T), relative humidity
235 (RH), solar radiation (SR) and precipitation (PP) sensors was set in the middle of the experimental
236 pollen source at 1.5 m above ground level (0.5 m above the canopy) while a 3D sonic anemometer
237 was set at 2.5 m above ground level (1.5 m above the canopy) (Table 1). The location of
238 meteorological sensors in the immediate vicinity of the pollen source was expected to provide the
239 data representative for the field conditions related to anthesis and pollen emission. Therefore, the
240 relationships between measured pollen concentrations and meteorological parameters should reveal
241 conditions that drive *Ambrosia* pollen emission processes. To know them is a prerequisite for
242 determining the function for mechanical description of the emission suitable to be used in
243 dispersion models.

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245

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Table 1. List of the equipment used for collecting data and the measurement characteristics.

Sensor	Manufacturer (and type of device)	Pcs.	Temporal resolution	Height (above ground level)	Locality and distance from the pollen source area	Information range
Pollen and spore trap	BURKARD SCIENTIFIC SporeWatch	2	7.5 min ¹	1.5 m	Backi Maglic (BM), center	Local
				6 m	BM, center	Local and Background
	LANZONI VPPS2000	3	60 min	1.5 m	BM, 20 m NW ²	Background
				1.5 m	BM, 15 m E ²	Background
				1.5 m	BM, 60 m E ³	Background
	LANZONI VPPS2010	3	60 min	roof-level	Sombor	Regional
roof-level				Vrbas	Regional	
roof-level				Novi Sad	Regional	
3D sonic anemometer	YOUNG 8100	1	20 Hz (2014) 10 Hz (2015-2016)	2.5 m	BM, center	Local
Thermo-Hygro Sensor + Shelter	YOUNG 41382+41003	1	1 Hz	1.5 m	BM, center	Local
Tipping Bucket Rain Gauge	YOUNG 52203	1	Yes/No rain (2014) 1 Hz (2015-2016)	1.5 m	BM, center	Local
Global Radiation Sensor	WILMERS Messtechnik	1	1 Hz	1.5 m	BM	Local

¹except on 1st and 2nd September 2015 at 6-12 AM when full rotation of drum set to 3h resulting in maximum resolution 1.07 min; ²only in 2015; ³in 2015-2016

247

248 Zink et al. (2013) identified temperature, relative humidity, turbulent kinetic energy and
 249 precipitation as the key factors for the parameterization of pollen emission processes. In order to
 250 examine the influence of the wind on pollen concentration we calculated the turbulent kinetic
 251 energy (TKE), as a measure of turbulence that lifts the pollen into the air. TKE was calculated per
 252 unit mass (Stull, 1988) as the sum of variances of all three wind components, u , v and w , in x , y and
 253 z direction, respectively (Equation 1).

$$254 \quad TKE = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{(u')^2} + \overline{(v')^2} + \overline{(w')^2}) \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

255 During the 2014 campaign, data from the tipping bucket rain gauge were impacted by a
 256 technical malfunction (the rain gauge was not unblocked properly at the setup), so the data can only
 257 be interpreted in a qualitative manner (yes/no precipitation). Also, the frequency of the sonic
 258 measurements was set at 20 Hz which was at the limit of the receiving rate of the data logger
 259 (WILMERS Messtechnik GmbH NDL485). Consequently, the actual receiving rate and thus the
 260 time resolution were not stable and fluctuated considerably but allowed estimation of dominant
 261 wind directions needed for setting Lanzoni VPPS2010 traps in the vicinity of the pollen source in
 262 2015 and 2016. Observed dominance of NW and E wind directions was confirmed by
 263 measurements also in 2015 and 2016. Since sonic data were not complete for calculating TKE, the
 264 analysis of the relationship between TKE and pollen concentrations was performed on 2015-2016

265 dataset when wind measurement frequency was set to 10 Hz, which ensured the logger was able to
266 receive the data from Sonic at any time resulting in a constant temporal resolution.

267

268 *2.4. Data analysis*

269

270 The study was focused on emissions from a known source, measured at 0.5 m above the canopy
271 (1.5 m above the ground). The analysis was performed using Python analytical libraries (JetBrains,
272 2017) and Microsoft Excel. Timestamps where data were missing (i.e. pollen concentration or
273 meteorological parameters) were omitted from the analysis. All timestamps used in this paper are
274 presenting local time, in CEST time zone. Meteorological data were averaged within 7.5-minute
275 intervals before the analysis.

276 At first, stationarity, periodicities and normality of the data were explored (Bendat and
277 Piersol, 2011). Due to the existence of the daily release cycle, the pollen emission process is time
278 variant. This can also be seen in our dataset. To confirm non-stationarity of the pollen dataset we
279 used the non-parametric reverse arrangement test that does not require any prior knowledge about
280 the distribution of the pollen release (Bendat and Piersol, 2011). The presence of periodic
281 components in the signal of pollen emission was detected by a visual inspection of the
282 autocorrelation function which showed evident periodic peaks within 24-hour period and a very
283 slow decrease for different time lags due to the non-stationarity of the data. As identified by the
284 D'Agostino-Pearson test (Pearson et al., 1977), the distribution of pollen concentration signal
285 deviates from the Gaussian distribution. It is interesting to note that even after removing non-
286 stationarity from the data using a composition of Box-Cox transformation (Brockwell and Davis,
287 2016) and differencing, data still deviated from the normal distribution. Therefore, all analysis was
288 conducted on the raw dataset with non-parametric statistics, while the implication of non-
289 stationarity is discussed in a later section.

290 Kendall rank correlation coefficient (τ) was calculated as a measure of statistical
291 dependence (Kendall, 1938) between the pollen concentration and meteorological data. The
292 correlation analysis was performed for entire days, on data limited to 6:00-16:00, which is the
293 period when major anthesis are expected (Martin et al., 2010) and on data limited to 9:00-12:00,
294 when the maximum emission is expected. Limiting the analysis to the main emission period aimed
295 at preventing the overestimation of the intensity of correlations resulting from existence of long
296 periods with very low values before the start and after the end of the daily emission (Sikoparija et
297 al., 2018).

298 In order to validate the findings of laboratory experiments by Bianchi et al. (1959) and the
299 emission parameterization designed by Zink et al. (2013), we tested the distribution of 7.5-minute
300 pollen concentrations for the ranges of temperature (in the intervals of 1 °C), relative humidity (in
301 the intervals of 5%) and TKE (in the intervals of 0.1 m² s⁻²). Since the analysis strived to explore
302 the characteristics of the emission from the source, we focused on the period from 6:00 to 16:00 as
303 the main emission period for *Ambrosia* (Martin et al., 2009; 2010).

304 Parameterization of the pollen emission requires a function for each meteorological variable
305 and pollen, as proposed in EMPOL (Zink et al., 2013). Since EMPOL was originally made for the
306 emission of birch pollen, but adaptable for different plant species, its authors highly recommended
307 using field experiments for tuning the parameter values in the functions. Here, we compared the
308 dependencies obtained from our measurements to the functions given in EMPOL. The relationships
309 that were not in accordance to functions given in EMPOL were assessed in detail and
310 parameterized. Curve_fit function from the *scipy.optimize* library in PyCharm (JetBrains, 2017) was
311 used to get the first guess values. Then we fine-tuned the model by varying the function parameters
312 to minimise the mean squared error between the calculated values and the average pollen
313 concentration, normalized to the maximum value from the distribution. Since we focused on the
314 emission from the plants, our parameterization was restricted to the daytime (i.e. solar radiation
315 greater than zero). Nevertheless, it was important to inhibit non-realistic emission in the afternoon
316 hours. This was achieved by introducing a function of diurnal emission cycle, which was calculated
317 as 1-y at each time step, where y is the percentage of the daily integral of airborne pollen
318 concentration (calculated from 7.5-minute measurements) released until a given timestamp.
319 According to common practice, the daily integral of airborne pollen concentration is estimated from
320 the pollen calendar (Sikoparija et al., 2018). Since there is a large uncertainty in the estimated
321 pollen production, the emission-parameterization model was evaluated for the daily emission
322 capacities ranging from minimum to maximum values of pollen production. Daily emission
323 capacity corresponds to the amount of pollen that can be emitted per day under perfect conditions
324 (i.e. $Q_{pollen,day}$ in EMPOL).

325 Finally, the results from the model were compared to measurements from 8 days without
326 precipitation selected from the peak of the pollen season in 2015 and 2016. These data were left out
327 from the model calibration. The first performance criterion was the conservation of mass, for which
328 we compared the daily integral of airborne pollen concentration (X) of modeled and measured data,
329 by calculating the relative error (Equation 2).

330
$$relative\ error = \frac{ABS|X_{modeled} - X_{measured}|}{X_{measured}} \times 100\ (\%) \quad (Equation\ 2)$$

331 The second one was the simultaneous occurrence of airborne pollen which we assessed by
332 performing correlation analysis, using Pearson and Kendall rank correlation coefficients. High
333 correlation indicates more simultaneous variation of the measured and modeled values. The
334 correlation coefficients are sensitive to the start of the emission and the shape of the daily profile.

335

336 **3. Results**

337

338 *3.1. Average pollen production per plant*

339

340 The average pollen production per plant in our experimental source was estimated to be 2.55×10^9
341 pollen grains (minimum = 2.68×10^8 and maximum = 1.59×10^{10}). Considering that 1-3 male
342 flowers per inflorescence mature and release pollen per day, and assuming that this takes place in
343 all male heads of all plants in our source, we have estimated possible daily emission capacity for
344 our source to range from 6.38×10^9 to 7.70×10^{11} pollen grains and used these values for testing
345 the emission parameterization model.

346

347 *3.2. Influence of the source*

348

349 Tenfold difference between records at different heights above the source (Fig. 2A and 2B) confirms
350 that the influence of background pollen on records at 0.5 m above canopy can be considered
351 neglectable and thus the airborne pollen recorded at 0.5 m above the source was taken as
352 representative for the emission. The influence of experimental *A. artemisiifolia* pollen source to
353 measurements at 0.5m above the canopy is also supported by tenfold lower records in Lanzoni
354 VPPS2010 traps measuring at 1.5 m in dominant wind directions around the source and by further
355 decrease in concentrations recorded in regional pollen traps situated at roof level in Novi Sad, Vrbas
356 and Sombor (Fig. 2C and 2D).

357 There was a simultaneous sharp increase of pollen concentrations in both traps situated
358 above the ragweed canopy (i.e. 0.5 m and 5 m), when the source was disturbed by mowing on 2nd
359 September 2015 and 1st September 2016 (Fig. 2 grey bars). This indicated a notable influence of our
360 source on records in both traps situated above the ragweed canopy. The dominance of our artificial
361 source was further confirmed by a sharp decrease in measurements at 0.5 m above the canopy on 3rd
362 September 2015 following the total removal of the source and on 2nd- 5th September 2016 following
363 the 50% reduction of the source.

364

365 Fig. 2. Daily pollen concentrations (pollen grains m^{-3}) (A) measured by Burkard Scientific
366 SporeWatch trap at 0.5m above the canopy, (B) measured by Burkard Scientific SporeWatch trap at
367 5m above the canopy (C) in the background air represented by average from measurements using
368 Lanzoni VPPS2010 traps at 1.5m above the ground in vicinity of pollen source area and (D) in the
369 regional air represented by average from measurements using Lanzoni VPPS2000 traps at roof level
370 in Novi Sad, Vrbas and Sombor (grey columns in A and B indicate days when source was disturbed
371 by mowing, also note tenfold difference in scale of y-axis).

372

373 3.3. Seasonality of the pollen emission and dispersion

374

375 There is a clear seasonality in the time series of daily pollen concentration resulting from regularity
376 in *A. artemisiifolia* flowering phenophase (Fig. 2). Because of the elimination of the source in the
377 end of 2015 and 2016 seasons, the best representation of the full flowering season was given in
378 2014. Pollen emission has a bell shape with the start at the end of July, peak at the end of August
379 and ends in mid-September. Analysed time series show statistically significant positive correlation
380 (Kendall rank correlation coefficients (τ) ≥ 0.62 , p-value $\leq 3.6 \times 10^{-15}$) confirming their
381 representativity for depicting progress of the *A. artemisiifolia* flowering phenophase in the study
382 region.

383

384 3.4. Hourly pollen distribution

385

386 Similarly, there is a regularity in the diurnal cycle (Fig. 3). Sharp increase in the emission
387 starts at about 7:00 and after the peak is reached at about 9:00-11:00, concentrations gradually
388 decrease. It is interesting to note that pollen was recorded even in the evening hours with distinctive
389 peaks until 23:00. The increase in temporal resolution from 1 h to 7.5 minutes reveals that during
390 the first peak, alternating periods of higher and lower concentrations are recorded. This suggests
391 puffed mode of release rather than continuous release. If the sampling resolution is further increased
392 to 1.07 minutes, additional variability in recorded concentrations can be seen during the main
393 emission period (Supplementary material Fig. S2).

394

395

396

397 Fig. 3. Boxplots of pollen concentration (pollen grains m⁻³) depicting the diurnal cycle of the pollen
 398 emission at 0.5 m above the canopy in the source area at (A) 1 hour and (B) 7.5-minute temporal
 399 resolution (whiskers are set to 5% and 95% while horizontal lines denote the median).

400

401 3.5. Influence of meteorological conditions

402

403 Meteorological parameters such as T, SR, TKE directly correlate with pollen emission while RH
 404 and PP correlate indirectly (Table 2). However, the applicability of correlations when analysing
 405 relationships between pollen data and meteorological conditions, that are expected to influence the
 406 emission, is limited. Long data series result in high significance of correlations ($p < 0.01$) but the
 407 intensity of the correlation is weak (Table 2). Further decrease in intensity when focusing on the
 408 main anthesis period (6:00-16:00) or the maximum emission period (9:00-12:00) suggests that there

409 is a low statistical linear dependence between meteorological conditions and pollen concentrations
 410 at 7.5-minute temporal resolution. Some correlations calculated for the maximum emission period
 411 are even statistically insignificant. Further analysis was therefore focused on understanding the
 412 simultaneous influence of different meteorological variables on pollen concentrations.

413

414 Table 2. Kendall rank correlation coefficients (τ) between meteorological parameters (T, RH, SR,
 415 TKE, PP) and pollen concentrations measured at 7.5-minute resolution and 0.5 m above the canopy
 416 in the source area, for three different periods. All values are significant at the 0.01 level (two tailed)
 417 if not underlined.

418

Dataset focused on 0:00-24:00

419

	Pollen	T	RH	SR	TKE	PP
Pollen	1					
T	0.27	1				
RH	-0.28	-0.74	1			
SR	0.42	0.51	-0.52	1		
TKE	0.31	0.30	-0.30	0.50	1	
PP	-0.03	-0.12	0.14	-0.04	0.07	1

420

421

422

423

Dataset focused on major anthesis period 6:00-16:00

424

	Pollen	T	RH	SR	TKE	PP
Pollen	1					
T	0.10	1				
RH	-0.09	-0.76	1			
SR	0.13	0.60	-0.62	1		
TKE	0.09	0.22	-0.25	0.36	1	
PP	-0.10	-0.16	0.18	-0.17	0.06	1

425

426

427

428

Dataset focused on maximum emission period 9:00-12:00

429

	Pollen	T	RH	SR	TKE	PP
Pollen	1					
T	0.05	1				
RH	<u>-0.02</u>	-0.66	1			
SR	<u>-0.01</u>	0.50	-0.53	1		
TKE	<u>0.02</u>	-0.12	0.06	0.11	1	
PP	-0.09	-0.16	0.17	-0.16	0.09	1

430

431

432

433

434

435 The distribution of pollen with temperature shows the expected profile, given as the product
 436 of two sigmoid functions, with maximum values in the interval 20-24°C (Fig. 4A). After a detailed
 437 day-by-day analysis, we could not identify limiting temperature thresholds that stop the emission
 438 once the daily cycle started, indicating that the correlation is rather statistical than causal. Both
 439 pollen emission and temperature may be influenced by other factors such as daylight.

440 The distribution of pollen with relative humidity shows that the largest emission is
 441 concurrent with the relative humidity ranging in the interval 55-85% and that the values around

442 95% can prevent the emission (Fig. 4B). The examples on how high relative humidity delays or
443 even switches off the emission after its start are given in the Supplementary material (Fig. S3).

444 Despite expecting that the puffed mode of release would significantly depend on the energy
445 available for the emission of pollen from its reservoir, there is no obvious regularity in pollen
446 distribution depending TKE, which in most cases was in the interval 0-0.5 m² s⁻² (Fig. 4C).
447 Although one could expect that the higher energy available for shaking the source and lifting the
448 pollen will result in higher pollen concentration, the relationship is not direct. Therefore, if other
449 factors do not prevent emission, the values of TKE even less than 0.1 m² s⁻² are providing sufficient
450 energy to lift the pollen into the air.

451 There were only 11 days with precipitation in the study period of years 2015 and 2016. As
452 expected, the rain removes pollen from the atmosphere and from the leaves and other surfaces.
453 However, measurements showed that the start of the rain often resulted in a sharp increase in
454 emission. The rain coincides with instability of the atmosphere that is shown by an increase of TKE.
455 Also, rain drops can physically shake the source and initiate the emission of pollen that remained in
456 the flowers, or lift the pollen that is accumulated on leaves and surrounding surfaces. This is clearly
457 depicted in two consecutive days (10th and 11th August 2016) when it rained in the evening hours
458 following the normal morning emission (Supplementary material Fig. S4). On the first day, arrival
459 of the front caused instability of the atmosphere which resulted in pollen emission in the evening
460 hours at 19:00-20:00. However, notable instability at 7:00 on the second day did not result in the
461 emission because former rain episodes washed out all pollen from the surrounding surfaces and the
462 relative humidity did not decrease under the threshold required for anthesis and emission from
463 ragweed flowers. Later in the evening hours on 11th August, another event of rain with coinciding
464 instability of the atmosphere resulted in the emission of pollen at 17:00-18:00, thus confirming the
465 importance of TKE for the emission of pollen from both the plant and the surrounding surfaces. On
466 the other hand, in Supplementary material Fig. S3A shows an example of increase in pollen
467 concentration when rain started, although the TKE notably decreased.

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477 Fig. 4. 7.5-minute pollen average concentration (columns) and its number of records (circles) at
 478 intervals of recorded (A) T and (B) RH for all three seasons and (C) TKE in 2015-2016. The
 479 numbers on the x-axes represent the lower boundary of the class.

480

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485 3.6. Parameterization of TKE function and model results

486

487 Field measurements confirmed that the distribution of pollen with temperature and the limiting
488 effect of relative humidity are conceptually in accordance with functions developed for EMPOL
489 emission parameterization (Zink et al., 2013), yet this was not the case regarding the influence of
490 TKE (Fig. 4). Parameterization of the influence of TKE needed modifications since measurements
491 showed that very low values of TKE can initiate the emission, sometimes with very high
492 concentrations of pollen (Fig. 4C). For that reason we calculated the distribution of the average
493 pollen concentration with TKE at the intervals of $0.01 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and focused on the data from early
494 emission period (06:00-10:00) to ensure the recorded pollen concentrations were predominately
495 related to the pollen release from the flowers (Supplementary material Fig. S5A). Results showed it
496 was possible to keep the original concept from EMPOL and use a sigmoid function (Equation 3).

497
$$f(x) = \frac{1}{(1+e^{-ax+b})} - c \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

498 The first guess values of parameters of the sigmoid function ($a = 4.02728603617$, $b =$
499 0.261944471458 and $c = 0.40648813275$) came from the fitting of the curve (Supplementary
500 material Fig. S5B). Fine-tuning of the parameters resulted in the function (Equation 4) that was
501 used to calculate emission.

502
$$f_{E,TKE} = \frac{1}{(1+e^{-4TKE+0.31})} - 0.4 \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

503 The model was used to estimate the pollen emission for the 8 days shown in Fig. 5 that were
504 not used in establishing the model. When comparing the measured and the modelled emission, the
505 Pearson correlation coefficient varied notably for different estimations of daily emission capacity
506 and for the different days (Fig. 5A). Strong correlations (greater than 0.6), existed in the range of
507 $45-75 \times 10^9$ pollen grains, while further increase of daily emission capacity resulted in the decrease
508 of correlation coefficient. This indicated a high sensitivity of the model to the daily emission
509 capacity. Kendall rank correlation coefficients were less sensitive to changes in emission capacity
510 yielding moderate or strong correlations (greater than 0.5), in the interval of $5-175 \times 10^9$ pollen
511 grains (Fig. 5B). Relative error dropped below 5% for the daily emission capacity larger than $40 \times$
512 10^9 pollen grains (Fig. 5C).

513

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519 Fig. 5. (A) Pearson and (B) Kendall rank correlation coefficient between modeled and measured
 520 pollen concentrations and (C) the relative error between modeled and measured daily integral of
 521 airborne pollen concentration, for the different daily estimation of emission capacity, for the eight
 522 days from the peak of the season.

523

524

525

526 4. Discussion

527

528 4.1. Characteristics of the *Ambrosia* pollen source

529

530 Although the same methodology was used, the average production of *Ambrosia* plants in the
531 analysed source was twice the estimate given by Fumanal et al. (2007), which is commonly used as
532 a reference for pollen production potential of the common ragweed. The large variability in pollen
533 production between individual plants and populations is related to multiple factors that can affect
534 plant fitness, ranging from genetic to environmental (Fumanal et al., 2007; Rogers et al., 2006;
535 Simard and Benoit, 2011; Simard and Benoit, 2012). With respect to the daily emission capacity,
536 we found that a common ragweed plant can release on average 2.13×10^8 pollen grains which is a
537 magnitude less than, to our knowledge, the only estimate of daily emission capacity available in the
538 literature (Bouillène and Bouillène, 1930). We must note here that our estimate assumes that all
539 racemes and male heads on the plants release pollen from at least 1-3 male flowers which makes
540 this the “worst case scenario”. Although there is a notable variability in estimated pollen production
541 for common ragweed, the daily emission capacity, when combined with the abundance and the
542 distribution of plants, is a valuable input parameter for numerical dispersion models. Nevertheless,
543 we would like to underline here that the daily emission capacity is not the same as the overall level
544 of the pollen flux because the latter is a product of the total amount of pollen that can be released
545 during a day and the atmospheric conditions that drive pollen release.

546

547 4.2. *Ambrosia* airborne pollen around the source

548

549 The amount of airborne ragweed pollen recorded in regional traps during the study period
550 corresponds to long term records on the Pannonian Plain (Sikoparija et al., 2018), making the study
551 seasons representative for the emission in the area considered as the most infected by ragweed in
552 Europe (Smith et al., 2013). Notably, higher concentrations of airborne *Ambrosia* pollen measured
553 at 0.5 m above canopy in the center of the pollen source area, compared to background
554 measurements, confirms the dominance of the local source and ensures that the variability captured
555 by measurements at the immediate vicinity of the canopy reflect the emission. This is in line with
556 the observation from Raynor et al. (1973), which showed that particles in the planetary boundary
557 layer are vertically well mixed after travelling only moderate distances (0.35 km) from their
558 sources. At least tenfold difference between emission levels and concentrations measured at
559 background and regional level agree with the pollen distribution profile determined for *Ambrosia*

560 (Raynor et al., 1970). The collected data, apart from being useful for exploring the emission, gives
561 an overview of potential exposure amounts in the close vicinity of a common ragweed pollen
562 source. This further emphasizes the problem that observed substantial differences in concentrations
563 at street and roof levels (Rantio-Lehtimäki et al., 1991; Spiekma et al., 2000) can pose to the
564 analysis of the real-life exposure in dose response surveys, making the personalized sampling a
565 more appropriate means of data collection (Werchan et al., 2018). The observed quantity of
566 airborne ragweed pollen in the vicinity of its source highlights the importance of eradicating
567 ragweed on smaller spatial scales to limit the exposure in inhabited areas (Katz and Carey, 2014). In
568 cities, the canyoning effect of houses and buildings (Peel et al., 2014) could limit the dispersion and
569 thus prolong exposure to allergenic pollen at the breathing level.

570

571 4.3. Seasonality and daily cycle

572

573 The analysis of airborne pollen concentrations has shown notable seasonality and diurnal regularity.
574 Resulting from the timing of ragweed's flowering phenophase, the seasonality of this phenophase is
575 significantly determined by the photoperiod (Deen et al., 1998). Because *Ambrosia* is a quantitative,
576 short-day species, development of its staminate flowers, as well as the start of the pollination, are
577 expected to be stable for a particular latitude (Storkey et al., 2014). This is further supported by
578 observation that locations in similar latitudes show similar changes in characteristics of flowering
579 that are driven by climate change (Ziska et al., 2011). This behaviour is confirmed when comparing
580 the observed timing of pollen season in our study with the season in the common ragweed's native
581 distribution range. About 10° difference in latitude between Backi Maglic (Serbia) and Tulsa (USA)
582 resulted in about 10-day difference in the timing of the pollen season (Howard and Levetin, 2014).

583 There is a clear diurnal cycle of *Ambrosia* airborne pollen emission. The majority of pollen
584 recorded in the period from 6:00-12:00 is in agreement with previous studies (Martin et al., 2010;
585 Ogden et al., 1969) and corresponds to biological mechanism behind anthesis (Martin et al., 2009).
586 As shown before (Martin et al., 2010; Ogden et al., 1969) the shape of the diurnal concentration
587 signal is notably affected by meteorological conditions. Our study clearly showed that relative
588 humidity is responsible for delaying emission resulting in later record of the modeled peak by
589 Martin et al. (2010). To our knowledge this is the first study that continuously measured airborne
590 pollen concentrations at temporal resolution below 1 h. Our measurements above the source
591 captured the bimodal shape of the pollen concentration signal, which results from the primary
592 emission from anthesis, followed by emission driven by pistilodium growth (Martin et al., 2009).
593 The increase of the temporal resolution from 1 h to 7.5 minutes provides more precise information

594 about the presence of the second peak and reveals that during the first peak alternating periods of
595 higher and lower concentrations are recorded (Fig. 3B). In addition, there is a concentration peak
596 commonly recorded in the evening hours. It is important to emphasize that recent findings in the
597 UV-based regulation mechanism for plant circadian clock (Meyer et al., 2017) suggest that an
598 internally-driven daily cycle could be considered as a crucial feature of the ragweed pollen emission
599 process and could be used as a feature in model development with an equal weight to other external
600 drivers (i.e. temperature, relative humidity etc.), like in the case of emission parameterization for
601 SILAM (Prank et al., 2013).

602 When temporal resolution of measurements is further increased from 7.5 minutes to 1.07
603 minutes the signal reveals notable variability suggesting that the *Ambrosia* field is not a continuous,
604 but rather puffed source that emits in a number of short term periods, when both plant internal and
605 environmental conditions are appropriate. High-frequency turbulence may lead to the puffed source
606 nature of the *Ambrosia* field. Atmospheric mixing is expected to eliminate this variability in roof-
607 level measurements. Further exposure studies will have to take into consideration such short-term
608 variations in concentrations near the source.

609

610 4.4. Parameterization of emission

611

612 Low intensity of Kendall correlations between pollen concentration and meteorological parameters
613 is expected since it represents the association between two different physical processes with
614 different dynamics of change (e.g. fast changes of pollen concentration between consecutive
615 timestamps are followed by slow changes of temperature, relative humidity etc.). The signs of
616 relationships are in line with the effects that meteorological factors are expected to have on
617 emission, i.e. humidity and precipitation hinders emission and pollen dispersion while temperature
618 and TKE foster the emission and dispersion (Table 2), as it is already shown for ragweed in several
619 aerobiological studies (Bartkova-Scevkova, 2003; Peternel et al., 2006; Puc, 2004). However, as
620 suggested by previous studies (Ritenberga et al., 2016; Sikoparija et al., 2018; Sofiev et al., 2015),
621 the interpretation of the results of correlation analysis between the pollen concentration and
622 meteorological parameters is difficult because the time series of pollen concentrations represents a
623 strongly non-stationary and non-ergodic process or because the relationship between pollen and
624 meteorological conditions might be nonlinear (Jones and Harrison, 2004) and depend on
625 simultaneous effect of several meteorological parameters.

626 We have confirmed that the functions describing the influence of temperature and relative
627 humidity on pollen emission given in EMPOL (Zink et al., 2013) are in accordance with the

628 distribution of our data (Fig. 4). Still, EMPOL was originally designed for the emission of birch
629 pollen. To adapt the EMPOL emission parameterization to ragweed, we calculated new parameter
630 values for the sigmoid function of emission depending on TKE using our measurements. However,
631 direct implementation of our new function in EMPOL is not possible because our function is based
632 on calibration of the data 0.5 m above the source and EMPOL was designed to be used in numerical
633 dispersion models that typically have their lowest model level at around 10m and horizontal
634 resolutions in the range of km.

635 Furthermore, we introduced a new function, describing the diurnal emission cycle, based on
636 the daily integral of airborne pollen concentration. A similar concept of emission based on diurnal
637 variations in pollen release has been presented by Prank et al. (2013).

638 We tested the estimated emission capacity with the new parameterization. Pearson
639 correlation coefficient seemed to be stricter than Kendall rank correlation coefficient, giving a more
640 suitable, narrow interval of the estimated emission capacity, for the 8 days selected. With the
641 relative error taken into consideration, $45-75 \times 10^9$ pollen grains per day are deemed as the most
642 reliable interval of emission capacity for the whole field, to be used in the model. This interval is a
643 very small segment from the beginning of the estimated range, which is not surprising since the
644 range was the result of the “worst-case scenario” when all inflorescences in all plants release pollen.
645 However, from Fig. 5A it is noticeable that for different days, maximal Pearson correlation
646 coefficient is obtained for different values of the emission capacity, indicating the variability in
647 pollen emission from day to day, even in the peak of the season. The increased CO₂ levels can have
648 a notable effect on pollen production (Rogers et al., 2006; Ziska and Caulfield, 2000) which makes
649 generalization of emission capacity to different regions difficult without an appropriate
650 experimental dataset.

651 We would like to underline here that in numerical weather prediction models (e.g. COSMO-
652 ART, in which EMPOL is used as emission parameterization scheme) TKE is calculated at around
653 10m above the ground applying sophisticated schemes and representative for a large area (the order
654 of km²). Therefore, using our function for TKE based emission parameterization in such models is
655 not possible. Emission parameterization could be based on other, nonlinear methods (e.g. artificial
656 neural networks).

657

658 **5. Conclusions**

659

660 Concentrations of airborne pollen at 0.5 m above the canopy (1.5 m above ground level) of a
661 homogenous field of *A. artemisiifolia* of $10 \times 10 \text{ m}^{-2}$ surface are roughly 20 times higher than

662 regional and background values, and thus are deemed suitable for exploring emission characteristics
663 of the given source. The increase in sampling resolution of the Burkard Scientific SporeWatch
664 revealed a notable amount of variance that remained hidden by the 1 h resolution of the standard
665 Hirst-type volumetric sampling. The pollen concentration signal supports puffed mode of release
666 rather than continuous one. The correlation between 7.5-minute airborne pollen concentrations and
667 meteorological parameters was weak and hence the analysis suggests nonlinear relationships
668 between meteorological conditions and pollen concentrations above the source.

669 It was important to introduce the function of diurnal emission cycle into the
670 parameterization of pollen emission. This function is based on the daily integral of airborne pollen
671 concentration, which can be estimated as the product of average daily pollen concentration and the
672 number of records, resulting from the sampling resolution during the day. In the areas where long
673 term aerobiological studies are performed, average daily pollen concentration can be taken from
674 pollen calendar.

675 We developed a function that describes the emission of *Ambrosia* pollen based on TKE. It
676 gives strong correlations with measurements assuming emission capacity of $45-75 \times 10^9$ pollen
677 grains per day and for the whole field. The strong influence of the emission capacity on the model
678 performance suggests further studies on the variability of this parameter in the future. Global maps
679 of *Ambrosia* biomass, possibly obtained by advanced remote sensing techniques, would be of great
680 interest.

681

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683

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696 **References**

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698 Alcázar, P., Comtois, P. (2000). The influence of sampler height and orientation on airborne
699 *Ambrosia* pollen counts in Montreal. *Grana* 39(6), 303–307.

700 BAF (1995). *Airborne Pollens and Spores: A Guide to Trapping and Counting*. The British
701 Aerobiology Federation, Aylesford.

702 Bartkova-Scevkova, J. (2003). The influence of temperature, relative humidity and rainfall on the
703 occurrence of pollen allergens (*Betula*, *Poaceae*, *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*) in the atmosphere
704 of Bratislava (Slovakia). *Int. J. Biometeorol.* 48, 1–5.

705 Bendat, J.S., Piersol, A.G. (2011). *Random data: analysis and measurement procedures* (Vol. 729).
706 John Wiley & Sons.

707 Bianchi, D.E., Schwemmin, D.J., Wagner, Jr W.H. (1959). Pollen release in the common ragweed
708 (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*). *Bot. Gaz.* 120, 235–243.

709 Bouillène, M., Bouillène, R. (1930). Recherches expérimentales sur l'agent toxique du pollen
710 d'*Ambrosia* div. sp. (Compositacées). *Bull. Acad. Roy. Belg.* 8, 1052-1072.

711 Bousquet, J. (2013). Foreward. In Sofiev, M., Bergman, C-K (eds.) *Allergenic Pollen: A Review of*
712 *the Production, Release, Distribution and Health Impacts*. Springer Verlag, vii. pp272.
713 ISBN978-94-007-4880-4.

714 Brockwell, P.J., Davis, R.A. (2016). *Introduction to time series and forecasting*. Springer.

715 Burba, G., Anderson, D. (2005). *A Brief Practical Guide to Eddy Covariance Flux Measurements:*
716 *Principles and Workflow Examples for Scientific and Industrial Applications*. Version 1.0.1.
717 LI-COR Biosciences. pp214. (retrieved on 28th October 2017 from
718 http://breeze.colorado.edu/ATOC6020/2014_Spring_files/Brief_Intro_Eddy_Covariance.pdf
719).

720 Chamecki, M., Meneveau, C. (2011). Particle boundary layer above and downstream of an area
721 source: scaling, simulations, and pollen transport. *J. Fluid Mech.* 683, 1–26.

722 Dahl, A., Strandhede, S.-O., & Wihl, J.-A. (1999). Ragweed-An allergy risk in Sweden?
723 *Aerobiologia*, 15(4), 293–297.

724 Deen, W., Hunt, L.A., Swanton, C.J. (1998). Photothermal time describes common ragweed
725 (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.) phenological development and growth. *WeedSci.* 46, 561–568.

726 Emberlin, J. (2000). Aerobiology. In: Busse, W.W., Holgate, S.T. (Eds.), *Asthma and Rhinitis*, vol.
727 2. Blackwell Science.

728 Fumanal, B., Chauvel, B., Bretagnolle, F. (2007). Estimation of pollen and seed production of
729 common ragweed in France. *Ann. Agric. Environ. Med.* 14, 233-236.

730 Galán, C., Aiatti, A., Bonini, M., Clot, B., Crouzy, B., Dahl, A., Fernandez-González, D.,
731 Frenguelli, G., Gehrig, R., Isard, S., Levetin, E., Li, D.W., Mandrioli, P., Rogers, C.A.,
732 Thibaudon, M., Sauliene, I., Skjoth, C., Smith, M., Sofiev, M. (2017) Recommended
733 terminology for aerobiological studies. *Aerobiologia* 33, 293-295.

734 Galán, C., Smith, M., Thibaudon, M., Frenguelli, G., Oteros, J., Gehrig, R., Berger, U., Clot, B. and
735 Brandao, R. (2014). Pollen monitoring: minimum requirements and reproducibility of
736 analysis. *Aerobiologia* 30, 385-395.

737 Hirst, J.M. (1952). An automatic volumetric spore trap. *Annals of Applied Biology* 39, 257–265.

738 Howard, L.E., Levetin, E. (2014). Ambrosia pollen in Tulsa, Oklahoma: aerobiology, trends, and
739 forecasting model development. *Ann. Allergy Asthma Immunol.* 113, 641-646.

740 JetBrains (2017). PyCharm. [online] JetBrains. Available at: <https://www.jetbrains.com/pycharm/>
741 [Accessed 10 October 2017]

742 Jones A.M., Harrison R.M. (2004). The effects of meteorological factors on atmospheric bioaerosol
743 concentrations—a review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 326, 151–180.

744 Katz, D.S.W., Carey, T.S. (2014). Heterogeneity in ragweed pollen exposure is determined by plant
745 composition at small spatial scales. *Sci. Total Environ.* 485, 435–440.

746 Kendall, M. (1938). A New Measure of Rank Correlation. *Biometrika*, 30. 81–89.

747 Martin, M.D., Chamecki, M., Brush, G.S. (2010). Anthesis synchronization and floral morphology
748 determine 5 diurnal patterns of ragweed pollen dispersal, *Agr. Forest Meteorol.* 150, 1307–
749 1317.

750 Martin, M.D., Chamecki, M., Brush, G.S., Meneveau, C., Parlange, M.B. (2009). Pollen clumping
751 and wind dispersal in an invasive angiosperm. *Am. J. Bot.* 96(9), 1–10.

752 Meyer, K., Köster, T., Nolte, C., Weinholdt, C., Lewinski, M., Grosse, I., Staiger, D. (2017).
753 Adaptation of iCLIP to plants determines the binding landscape of the clockregulated RNA-
754 binding protein AtGRP7. *Genome Biol.* 18, 1-22.

755 Ogden, E.C., Hayes, J.V., Raynor, G.S. (1969). Diurnal patterns of pollen emission in *Ambrosia*,
756 *Phleum*, *Zea* and *Ricinus*. *Am. J. Bot.* 56(1), 16–21.

757 Pearson, E.S., Agostino, R.B., Bowman, K.O. (1977). Tests for departure from normality:
758 Comparison of powers. *Biometrika*, 64(2), 231-246.

759 Peden, D., Reed, C.E., (2010). Environmental and occupational allergies. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.*
760 125, S150–S160.

761 Peel, R.G., Kennedy, R., Smith, M., Hertel, O. (2014). Do urban canyons influence street level
762 grass pollen concentrations? *Int. J. Biometeorol.* 58(6), 1317-25.

763 Peternel, R., Culig, J., Hrga, I., Hercog, P. (2006). Airborne ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.)
764 pollen concentrations in Croatia, 2002–2004. *Aerobiologia* 22, 161-168.

765 Prank, M., Chapman, D.S., Bullock, J.M., Soler, J.B., Berger, U., Dahl, A., Jäger, S., Kovtunen,
766 I., Magyar, D., Niemelä, S., Rantio-Lehtimäki, A., Rodinkova, V., Sauliene, I., Severova,
767 E., Sikoparija, B., Sofiev, M. (2013). An operational model for forecasting ragweed pollen
768 release and dispersion in Europe. *Agr. Forest Meteorol.* 182, 43-53.

769 Puc M (2004). Ragweed pollen in the air of Szczecin. *Ann Agric Environ Med* 11, 53-57.

770 Rantio-Lehtimäki, A., Koivikko, A., Kupias, R., Mäkinen, Y., Pohjola, A. (1991). Significance of
771 sampling height of airborne particles for aerobiological information. *Allergy* 46(1), 68–76.

772 Raynor, G.S., Eugene, B.S., Ogden, C., Hayes, J.V. (1968). Effect of a local source on ragweed
773 pollen concentrations from background sources. *J. Allergy* 41, 217-225.

774 Raynor, G.S., Hayes, J., Ogden, E.C. (1970). Experimental data on ragweed pollen dispersion and
775 deposition from point and area sources. Technical Report 50224 (T-564), Brookhaven
776 National Laboratory, 33pp.

777 Raynor, G.S., Ogden, E.C., Hayes, J.V. (1973). Variation in ragweed pollen concentration to a
778 height of 108 meters. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* 51(4), 199–207.

779 Ritenberga, O., Sofiev, M., Kirillova, V., Kalnina, L., Genikhovich, E. (2016) Statistical modelling
780 of non-stationary processes of atmospheric pollution from natural sources: example of birch
781 pollen. *Agr.Forest Meteorol.* 226–227, 96–107.

782 Rogers, C., Wayne, P.M., Macklin, E.A., Muilenberg, M.L., Wagner, C.J., Epstein, P.R., Bazzaz,
783 B.A. (2006). Interaction of the onset of spring and elevated atmospheric CO₂ on ragweed
784 (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.) pollen production. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 114, 865–869.

785 Scheifinger, H., Belmonte, J., Celenk, S., Damialis, A., Dechamp, C., Garcia-Mozo, H., Gehrig, R.,
786 Grewling, L., Halley, JM., Hogda, KA., Jäger, S., Karatzas, K., Karlsen, SR., Koch, E.,
787 Pauling, A., Peel, R., Sikoparija, B., Smith, M., Galán-Soldevilla, C., Thibaudon, M.,
788 Vokou, D., de Weger, L. (2013). Monitoring, modelling and forecasting of the pollen
789 season. In Sofiev, M., Bergman, C-K (eds.) *Allergenic Pollen: A Review of the Production,*
790 *Release, Distribution and Health Impacts.* Springer Verlag, 71-126.

791 Sikoparija, B., Marko, O., Panić, M., Jakovetić, D., Radišić, P. (2018). How to prepare a pollen
792 calendar for forecasting daily pollen concentrations of *Ambrosia*, *Betula* and *Poaceae*?
793 *Aerobiologia* (in press).

794 Simard, M.J., Benoit, D.L. (2011). Effect of repetitive mowing on common ragweed (*Ambrosia*
795 *artemisiifolia* L.) pollen and seed production. *Ann. Agric. Environ. Med.* 18, 55–62.

796 Simard, M.J., Benoit, D.L. (2012). Potential pollen and seed production from early- and late-
797 emerging common ragweed in corn and soybean. *Weed Technol.* 26, 510–516.

798 Skjøth, C.A. Smith, M., Sikoparija, B., Stach, A., Myszkowska, D., Kasprzyk, I., Radisic, P.,
799 Stjepanovic, B., Hrga, I., Apatini, D., Magyar, D., Páldy, A., Ianovici, N. (2010) A method
800 for producing airborne pollen source inventories: An example of *Ambrosia* (ragweed) on the
801 Pannonian Plain. *Agr. Forest Meteorol.* 150, 1203-1210.

802 Smith, M., Cecchi, L., Skjøth, C.A., Karrer, G., Sikoparija, B. (2013). Common ragweed: A threat
803 to environmental health in Europe. *Environ. Int.* 61, 115-126.

804 Sofiev, M., Siljamo, P., Ranta, H., and Rantio-Lehtimäki, A. (2006). Towards numerical fore-
805 casting of long-range air transport of birch pollen: theoretical considerations and a feasibility
806 study: *Int. J. Biometeorol.*, 50, 392-402.

807 Sofiev, M., Berger, U., Prank, M., Vira, J., Arteta, J., Belmonte, J., Bergmann, K.-C., Chéroux, F.,
808 Elbern, H., Friese, E., Galan, C., Gehrig, R., Khvorostyanov, D., Kranenburg, R., Kumar,
809 U., Marécal, V., Meleux, F., Menut, L., Pessi, a.-M., Robertson, L., Ritenberga, O.,
810 Rodinkova, V., Saarto, a., Segers, a., Severova, E., Sauliene, I., Siljamo, P., Steensen, B.M.,
811 Teinmaa, E., Thibaudon, M., Peuch, V.-H. (2015). MACC regional multi-model ensemble
812 simulations of birch pollen dispersion in Europe. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 15, 8115–8130.

813 Sofiev, M. (2017). On impact of transport conditions on variability of the seasonal pollen index.
814 *Aerobiologia* 33, 167–179.

815 Spijksma, F.T.M., van Noort, P., Nikkels, H. (2000). Influence of nearby stands of *Artemisia* on
816 street-level versus roof-top-level ratio's of airborne pollen quantities. *Aerobiology* 16(1),
817 21–24.

818 Storkey, J., Stratonovitch, P., Chapman, D.S., Vidotto, F., Semenov, M.A. (2014). A Process-Based
819 Approach to Predicting the Effect of Climate Change on the Distribution of an Invasive
820 Allergenic Plant in Europe. *PLoS ONE* 9(2), e88156.

821 Stull, R.B. (1988) An introduction to boundary layer meteorology. Springer Netherlands.

822 Werchan, M., Sehlinger, T., Goergen, F., Bergmann, K-C. (2018). The pollator: a personal pollen
823 sampling device. *Allergo J. Int.* 27, 1-3.

824 Zink, K., Pauling, A., Rotach, M.W., Vogel, H., Kaufmann, P., Clot., B. (2013). EMPOL 1.0: a new
825 parameterization of pollen emission in numerical weather prediction models. *Geosci. Model*
826 *Dev. Discuss.* 6, 3137 – 3178.

827 Ziska, L.H., Caulfield, F.A. (2000). Rising CO₂ and pollen production of common ragweed
828 (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*), a known allergy-inducing species: implications for public health.
829 *Aust. J. Plant Physiol.* 27, 893–898.

830 Ziska L., Knowlton K., Rogers C., Dalan D., Tierney N., Elder, MA., Filley, W., Shropshire, J.,
831 Ford, L.B., Hedberg, C., Fleetwood, P., Hovanky, K.T., Kavanaugh, T., Fulford, G., Vrtisk,
832 R.F., Patz, J.A., Portnoy, J., Coates, F., Bielory, L., Frenz, D. (2011). Recent warming by
833 latitude associated with increased length of ragweed pollen season in central North America.
834 P. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA 108, 4248–4251.

Supplementary Material

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Graphical Abstract (for review)

Highlights

- Concentrations above the source are roughly 20 times higher than background values
- Pollen production per day was in range from 6.38×10^9 to 7.70×10^{11} pollen grains
- Shift in temporal resolution from 1 h to 7.5 minutes reveals puffed mode of release
- Turbulent kinetic energy less than $0.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ is sufficient for lifting pollen

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